

FIBER OPTICS TRENDS AND STRATEGIC APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The growing global ubiquity of commercial fiber optics transmission systems, and the continuing use of circuits derived from these systems for the terrestrial portion of the strategic communication suites of DoD and other government agencies concerned with National Security and Emergency Preparedness (NS/EP) means that fiber optics will play an increasing role in these applications.

This paper presents first the historical and forecasted trends in fiber optic technology, with implications on the expected cost of such transmission systems. The latest example of technology advances, the optical amplifier, is highlighted. The world-wide deployment of fiber optic systems is illustrated and applications to DoD discussed. The Defense Commercial Telecommunications Network (DCTN), which started as a mix of satellite and landline circuits and is now trending to an all fiber network, is presented as an example.

The spectrum of threats to NS/EP telecommunications is presented, as are the implications of the reduced emphasis on a massive nuclear attack. Finally, the potential roles of embedded network intelligence and of standards such as Synchronous Optical Network (SONET) in improving end-to-end survivability of critical NS/EP connectivity is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Communications for strategic purposes, as used in this paper, embraces connectivity for military command and control (C²) needs but also includes that for other Government departments and agencies which may be involved during times of national stress or crisis. Communications needed during these situations are referred to by the acronym NS/EP (National Security/Emergency Preparedness) and, of course, constitute the most crucial need for Government communications. There are, however, continuing requirements for strategic communications even during periods of relative global calm.

The strategic communication requirements of the military and civilian agencies meet at the level of the National Command Authority, at whose apex is the President. Below that we

have the communication networks of the Defense Department itself; of the Joint Chiefs of Staff; and of the Army, Navy, Air Force, and their subordinate commands; the intelligence community, the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the Departments of State, Treasury, Transportation, etc. The communication assets serving these organizations are composed of a mixture of dedicated and common carrier facilities. Communications technologies include satellite systems, HF radio, terrestrial line-of-sight microwave, and cables - both terrestrial and undersea. While the RF systems may be owned by the Government, circuits on cables are almost invariably provided by commercial carriers.

The commercial carriers themselves are becoming more and more fiber optics dominated, and thus terrestrial strategic communications is also. For reasons of survivability from a spectrum of threats, organizations requiring strategic communications will always complement their terrestrial connectivity with radio and/or satellite systems. However, the latter two will likely find themselves playing a relatively smaller role as fiber optics technology evolves and its per circuit costs continue to decline. In what follows we will discuss those trends, and present the current situation generally in terms of fiber's ubiquity. We will introduce the range of threats to fiber systems carrying strategic communications and indicate the influence of the changing threat and changing nature of the networks on Government NS/EP needs. Finally, we will make a few observations about the ever wider acceptance of global standards and the potential impact on NS/EP communications.

FIBER OPTICS TRENDS

The basic reason for fiber's popularity is captured in Figure 1. The System Performance curve shows a doubling of the product of maximum bit-rate and regenerator spacing every year since the first year of commercial fiber systems availability. (This represents achievements of actual systems, not what had been accomplished in the laboratory). By contrast, the same measure for other transmission systems doubled roughly every eight years; lightwave passed those systems in bit-rate regenerator-spacing product almost as soon as it was first deployed. In other words, fiber optics performance exceeds that of other systems and is pulling

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away exponentially at eight times the rate.

Optics technology for communications is still a very new field: we are on the steep slope of the "learning curve" compared to the other technologies. Thus, in a recent comparison, the latest technology for both satellites and fiber cable systems cost about the same in first cost or annual operations, but the capacity of the latter and the shorter useful lifetime of the former favored fiber on a channel-per-unit-time basis by about four-to-one.

FIGURE 1 Performance and Cost Trends of Lightwave Systems

One recent example of technology advances in the fiber optics transmission arena is that of the optical amplifier (OA). Figure 2 shows a schematic of what a version of an OA looks like. It basically consists of a length of glass fiber, the core of which is doped with a rare-earth named Erbium, and an external pump laser. Erbium, it's been found, can be raised to a set of excited states by illumination at 1.48 microns (μm). The lifetimes of those states are several milliseconds, after which decay occurs at wave lengths around 1.55 microns. This decay, however, can be stimulated to occur by another lightsource at 1.55 microns, just as in a laser. That is, if a light pulse comes from the outside, as shown in Figure 2, it stimulates more and more energy at that wave length as it passes through the Erbium-doped region, and depending on the latter's length, the energy of the pulse can rise several tens of dBs. In fact, we need to isolate this section of the cable so that some part of the energy does not reflect back into the doped region again, get amplified still further, reflect, etc. and act like a laser.

FIGURE 2 Typical Optical Amplifier Design

It's also important to point out why the OA is useful. With today's fibers, the distance a pulse can travel before dispersion results in unacceptable intersymbol interference is many times that due to simple attenuation. With dispersion limits, the pulse needs to be regenerated; before that happens, however, we need only to amplify the pulse to assure its detection at the regenerator receiver. Thus, we can substitute the simple OA for the regenerative repeaters which otherwise would lie between those at the dispersion limits. We save capital, power and power costs, maintenance costs, and gain in end-to-end reliability.

As stated earlier, the OA is one of the latest examples of new concepts we are encountering as we climb the steep part of the learning curve on fiber optics. It is advances such as these which continue to give fiber optics its very substantial edge over other transmission media, and the result has been a revolution in the character of the terrestrial telecommunications. Figure 3 shows the fiber optics deployed by AT&T in late 1990. It's worthwhile to note that in 1985 the only fiber systems were one which connected Boston through NYC and Washington to Richmond, one which ran from San Francisco to Los Angeles, plus two short runs in Texas.

FIGURE 3 1990 AT&T Fiber Network

The links shown in Figure 3 denote the physical connections between locations, not the logical (end-to-end) connections. Because of cross-connection limitations and switch routing rules, standard calls between any two locations can use only a restricted number of intermediate switches as they route through these networks. That is, complete interconnection by every possible path, even within one commercial carrier's network, is not generally possible. This has implications on strategic communications which we will mention below.

Figure 4 displays the present and near-future deployment of undersea fiber optic cables. Once again, the pace at which this application of lightwave technology is growing is astonishing. The first AT&T fiber optic trans-Atlantic cable, TAT-8, was completed only a few years ago and, as can be seen from the figure, not only is it no longer the only one, it is slated to be joined with many more within the next three years.

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FIGURE 4 Undersea Fiber Optic Cable

Returning to CONUS and to communication services for strategic needs, the AT&T portion of the fiber deployment shown in Figure 3 serves as the base for the leased connectivity which makes up the Defense Commercial Telecommunication Network (DCTN). DCTN is currently being combined with AUTOVON to form what is called the Defense Switched Network (DSN). DSN, whose sites are shown in Figure 5, is a C² communication capability provided by AT&T under contract to the Defense Information Systems Agency (DISA). Of significance to the subject of this paper is the fact that DCTN began as a network in 1986 which was economically engineered to employ both satellite and cable transmission media. The DCTN/DSN design and costs are under constant review by DISA and AT&T, and - as further evidence of the ubiquity of fiber - DSN is now almost completely served by light-guide.

FIGURE 5 DCTN/DSN Sites

THREATS TO STRATEGIC COMMUNICATIONS; RESPONSES

The nature of strategic communications is such that survivability of end-to-end connectivity is vital. As mentioned, it is for this reason that multiple communication media are used in most strategic networks. In this paper, we will restrict ourselves to the classes of physical threats which impact fiber optic transmission systems considered as a

component of commercial carrier's networks serving strategic customers with leased circuits and/or switched services on the public network.

Certainly the threat which dominated all others for the last four decades - well before fiber optics - has been that of a nuclear attack. The effects of blast, heat, fallout radiation, and electromagnetic pulse (EMP) have concerned those involved in strategic communications since then. While there were studies earlier, the most recent and sustained evaluations of these effects on commercial carriers networks have taken place in the last decade under the aegis of the National Communications System (NCS). NCS is a Government organization whose manager is also the Director of DISA. NCS serves 23 federal departments and agencies with NS/EP communication concerns. NCS has sponsored a multi-pronged approach to these problems: one part involving assessment of nuclear effects on elements of commercial telecommunications networks; another on programs which maximize end-to-end connectivity under threat conditions; still another to monitor disruptive events impacting NS/EP communication capabilities and to be able to direct - when necessary - restoration and reconstitution of those networks.

To elaborate slightly on the first of these, extensive analytic and full-scale simulation assessments have been made, particularly as regards fallout and EMP effects, on a wide variety of telecommunications equipment: four-wire digital carrier, channel banks, local and toll switches, active cross-connect and multiplex gear, and - most relevantly - on commercially available fiber systems. While the detailed results per se are sensitive, we can observe that NCS is going ahead with the second part of its thrust, as mentioned above. This effort, in short, is to create - solely for NS/EP crisis purposes - routing and signaling capabilities and priority service within commercial carriers' networks which would enhance call completion under threat conditions. Since these approaches deal with switching and signaling, we will not discuss them further here.

Other threats to NS/EP communications, while less likely to cause massive damage to commercial telecommunications, are also of concern if they sever vital links. Widespread sabotage, along with multi-warhead nuclear attack, is now considered less likely by many, but the threats of earthquake, hurricanes, and floods are still with us. Because fiber optics offers such large bandwidth, commercial networks now tend to have fewer routes with heavier circuit cross-sections per route. Because of this, the connectedness of commercial networks has diminished and regional disruptions of the type just identified can have impacts on NS/EP traffic between points well away from the disaster. There are, however, countervailing technological forces which can be brought into play: the digital cross-connect capability already at many nodes in these all digital networks, and the relative ease of placing network reconfiguration logic at each node. While AT&T of course has its own systems and operations plans for restoration of service, NCS is currently sponsoring a study of

network management of stressed intelligent networks to understand better the role which Government may play in assuring priority restoration specifically of disrupted NS/EP communications, and to develop relevant criteria and standards. One example of the potential value of standards is the adoption of those of Synchronous Optical Network (SONET) by the various carriers and manufacturers of telecommunications equipment. SONET capability is currently available in most carriers' networks to varying degrees. Full adoption would allow cross-connection of fiber-borne channels among all carriers, today impossible because of separate and proprietary protocols. While the practical realization of such added NS/EP restoration capability probably faces many hurdles, it is likely that technology will not be one of them.

SUMMARY

Fiber optics technology has spawned a revolution, and its impact on both commercial and strategic communications will likely continue to be dramatic. One effect has been to reduce the connectedness of the commercial networks and thus of communications by the Government organizations which rely on them. This, in turn, means that responses to the threat environment are still required although the probability assigned to the worst of the NS/EP threats may have diminished. International standards and the increasing use of distributed intelligence in the networks offer new opportunities to minimize disruptive effects on strategic communications, whatever the threat.

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